

SENSORIZED WARFIGHTER WEAPON PLATFORM IOT MAKING THE FOG OF WAR OBSOLETE

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ABSTRACT

Security is always a main concern in every domain, due to a rise in crime rate in a crowded event or suspicious lonely areas. Abnormal detection and monitoring have major applications of computer vision to tackle various problems. Due to growing demand in the protection of safety, security and personal properties, needs and deployment of video surveillance systems can recognize and interpret the scene and anomaly events play a vital role in intelligence monitoring. This paper implements automatic gun (or) weapon detection using a convolution neural network (CNN) based SSD and Faster RCNN algorithms. Proposed implementation uses two types of datasets. One dataset, which had pre-labelled images and the other one is a set of images, which were labelled manually. Results are tabulated, both algorithms achieve good accuracy, but their application in real situations can be based on the trade-off between speed and accuracy.

INTRODUCTION

Weapon or Anomaly detection is the identification of irregular, unexpected, unpredictable, unusual events or items, which is not considered as a normally occurring event or a regular item in a pattern or items present in a dataset and thus different from existing patterns. An anomaly is a pattern that occurs differently from a set of standard patterns. Therefore, anomalies depend on the phenomenon of interest. Object detection uses feature extraction and learning algorithms or models to recognize instances of various category of objects. Proposed implementation focuses on accurate gun detection and classification. Also concerned with accuracy, since a false alarm could result in adverse responses. Choosing the right approach required to make a proper trade-off between accuracy and speed. Figure 1 shows the methodology of weapons detection using deep learning. Frames are extracted from the input video. Frame differencing algorithm is applied and bounding box created before the detection of

object. The flow of object detection and tracking as shown in figure 2. Dataset is created, trained and fed to object detection algorithm. Based on application suitable detection algorithm (SSD or fast RCNN) chosen for gun detection. The approach addresses a problem of detection using various machinelearning models like Region Convolutional Neural Network (RCNN), Single Shot Detection (SSD).

LITERATURE SURVEY

Wei Liu et al., “SSD: Single Shot MultiBox Detector”, European Conference on Computer Vision, Volume 169, pp 20-31 Sep. 2017.

The plan is to establish an integrated system that can manage high-quality visual information and also detect weapons quickly and efficiently. It is obtained by integrating ARM-based computer vision and optimization algorithms with deep neural networks able to detect the presence of a threat. The whole system is connected to a Raspberry Pi module, which will capture live broadcasting and evaluate it using a deep convolutional neural network. Due to the intimate interaction between object identification and video and image analysis in real-time objects, By generating sophisticated ensembles that incorporate various low-level picture features with high-

level information from object detection and scenario classifiers, their performance can quickly plateau. Deep learning models, which can learn semantic, high-level, deeper features, have been developed to overcome the issues that are present in optimization algorithms. It presents a review of deep learning based object detection frameworks that use Convolutional Neural Network layers for better understanding of object detection. The Mobile-Net SSD model behaves differently in network design, training methods, and optimization functions, among other things. The crime rate in suspicious areas has been reduced as a consequence of weapon detection. However, security is always a major concern in human life.

D. Erhan et al., “Scalable Object Detection Using Deep Neural Networks,” IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition(CVPR),2014.

Deep convolutional neural networks have recently achieved state-of-the-art performance on a number of image recognition benchmarks, including the ImageNet Large-Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC-2012). The winning model on the localization sub-task was a network that predicts a single bounding box and a confidence score for each object

category in the image. Such a model captures the whole-image context around the objects but cannot handle multiple instances of the same object in the image without naively replicating the number of outputs for each instance. In this work, we propose a saliency-inspired neural network model for detection, which predicts a set of class-agnostic bounding boxes along with a single score for each box, corresponding to its likelihood of containing any object of interest. The model naturally handles a variable number of instances for each class and allows for crossclass generalization at the highest levels of the network. We are able to obtain competitive recognition performance on VOC2007 and ILSVRC2012, while using only the top few predicted locations in each image and a small number of neural network evaluations. Object detection is one of the fundamental tasks in computer vision. A common paradigm to address this problem is to train object detectors which operate on a subimage and apply these detectors in an exhaustive manner across all locations and scales.

Ruben J Franklin et.al., “Anomaly Detection in Videos for Video Surveillance Applications Using Neural Networks,”

International Conference on Inventive Systems and Control,2020.

Security is always a main concern in every domain, due to a rise in crime rate in the crowded event or suspicious lonely areas. Abnormal detection and monitoring have major applications of computer vision to tackle various problems. Due to growing demand in the protection of safety, security and personal properties, the needs and deployment of video surveillance systems can recognize and interpret the scene and anomaly events play a vital role in intelligence monitoring. Anomaly detection is a technique used to distinguish various patterns and identify unusual patterns with a minimal period, this pattern is called outliers. Surveillance videos can capture a variety of realistic anomalies. Anomaly detection in video surveillance involves breaking down the whole process into three layers, which are video labelers, image processing, and activity detection. Hence, anomaly detection in videos for video surveillance application gives assured results in regards to real-time scenarios. In this paper, we anomaly was detected in images and videos with an accuracy of 98.5 %.

EXISTING SYSTEM

Weapon detection using Artificial Intelligence (AI) and deep learning has become an integral part of modern security applications. In the existing system, advanced computer vision techniques are employed to analyze video feeds and identify potential threats in real-time. Deep learning models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), are trained on extensive datasets containing images and videos of various weapons to enable accurate recognition.

The system typically involves preprocessing the video streams to extract relevant frames and then passing them through the trained neural network for object detection. These models can discern the subtle features and patterns associated with weapons, distinguishing them from regular objects. Additionally, recurrent neural networks or temporal models may be incorporated to enhance the system's ability to track and identify weapons over consecutive frames, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the security scenario.

Furthermore, the system is often designed to integrate with existing security infrastructure, such as surveillance cameras and access control systems. Once a potential threat is detected, the system can trigger automated responses, such as alert notifications to security personnel, law enforcement agencies, or activating other security protocols.

While the existing system has shown significant advancements in improving security measures, ongoing research and

development are essential to refine and expand its capabilities. This includes addressing challenges such as false positives, optimizing real-time processing speed, and adapting to diverse environments and lighting conditions. As technology evolves, the integration of AI and deep learning in weapon detection continues to play a crucial role in enhancing overall security measures in public spaces, critical infrastructure, and high-risk environments.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system for weapon detection using Artificial Intelligence (AI) and deep learning aims to enhance security applications by leveraging advanced technological capabilities. The system incorporates deep learning algorithms, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to analyze images or video streams in real-time and identify the presence of weapons accurately. This technology enables automated surveillance and threat detection, reducing the reliance on human operators and enhancing overall security measures.

In this system, the deep learning model is trained on a diverse dataset of images containing various types of weapons, allowing it to learn intricate patterns and features associated with different armaments. The model is fine-tuned to achieve high accuracy and robust performance across different environmental

conditions and camera perspectives. The training process enables the system to generalize well, ensuring reliable weapon detection in real-world scenarios.

The integration of AI-driven weapon detection contributes to a proactive security approach by providing timely alerts and responses to potential threats. The system can be deployed in critical areas such as transportation hubs, public venues, and sensitive facilities where rapid identification of weapons is crucial. Moreover, the technology can be seamlessly integrated with existing surveillance systems, creating a force multiplier effect and enhancing the overall efficiency of security personnel.

One of the key advantages of this proposed system is its ability to adapt and evolve through continuous learning. Periodic updates to the deep learning model based on new data ensure that the system remains effective against emerging threats and variations in weapon designs. Additionally, the incorporation of AI-driven weapon detection aligns with the broader trend of smart security solutions, fostering a safer and more secure environment by leveraging cutting-edge technologies to address evolving security challenges.

Block diagram

NODE-MCU

ESP32

ESP32 is a single 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi-and-Bluetooth combo chip designed with the TSMC ultra-low-power 40 nm technology. It is designed to achieve the best power and RF performance, showing robustness, versatility and reliability in a wide variety of applications and power scenarios. The ESP32 series of chips includes ESP32-D0WD-V3, ESP32-D0WDQ6-V3, ESP32-D0WD, ESP32-D0WDQ6, ESP32-D2WD, ESP32-S0WD, and ESP32-U4WDH, among which, ESP32-D0WD-V3, ESP32-D0WDQ6-V3, and ESP32-U4WDH are based on ECO V3 wafer

RELAY MODULE

Relay modules are simply circuit boards that house one or more relays. They come in a variety of shapes and sizes, but are most commonly rectangular with 2, 4, or 8 relays mounted on them, sometimes even up to a 16 relays.

Relay modules contain other components than the relay unit. These include [indicator LEDs](#), [protection diodes](#), transistors, resistors, and other parts. But what is the module relay, which makes the bulk of the device? You may ask. Here are facts to note about it:

- A relay is an electrical switch that can be used to control devices and systems that use higher voltages. In the case of module relay, the mechanism is typically an [electromagnet](#).
- The relay module input voltage is usually DC. However, the electrical load that a relay will control can be either AC or DC, but essentially within the limit levels that the relay is designed for.
- A relay module is available in an array of input voltage ratings: It can be a 3.2V or 5V relay module for low power switching, or it can be a 12 or 24V relay module for heavy-duty systems.
- The relay module information is normally printed on the surface of the device for ready reference. This includes the input voltage rating, switch voltage, and current limit.

L293D DRIVER MODULE

L293D is a typical Motor driver or Motor Driver IC which allows DC motor to drive on either direction. L293D is a 16-pin IC which can control a set of two DC motors simultaneously in any direction. It means that you can control two [DC motor](#) with a single L293D IC. Dual H-bridge *Motor Driver integrated circuit (IC)*.

The l293d can drive small and quiet big motors as well, check the Voltage Specification at the end of this page for more info.

You can Buy L293D IC in any electronic shop very easily and it costs around 70 Rupees (INR) or around 1 \$ Dollar (approx Cost) or even lesser cost. You can find the necessary pin diagram, working, a circuit diagram, Logic description and Project as you read through.

MOTOR:

A DC motor (Direct Current motor) is the most common type of motor. DC motors normally have just two leads, one positive and one negative. If you connect these two leads directly to a battery, the motor will

rotate. If you switch the leads, the motor will rotate in the opposite direction.

Warning – Do not drive the motor directly from Arduino board pins. This may damage the board. Use a driver Circuit or an IC.

We will divide this chapter into three parts –

- Just make your motor spin
- Control motor speed
- Control the direction of the spin of DC motor

GSM (Global System for Mobile communications)

GSM (Global System for Mobile communications) is a cellular network, which means that mobile phones connect to it by searching for cells in the immediate vicinity. GSM networks operate in four different frequency ranges. Most GSM networks operate in the 900 MHz or 1800 MHz bands. Some countries in the Americas use the 850 MHz and 1900 MHz bands because the 900 and 1800 MHz frequency bands were already allocated.

The rarer 400 and 450 MHz frequency bands are assigned in some countries, where these frequencies were previously used for first-generation systems.

GSM-900 uses 890–915 MHz to send information from the mobile station to the base station (uplink) and 935–960 MHz for the other direction (downlink), providing 124 RF channels (channel numbers 1 to 124) spaced at 200 kHz. Duplex spacing of 45 MHz is used. In some countries the GSM-900 band has been extended to cover a larger frequency range. This 'extended GSM', E-GSM, uses 880–915 MHz (uplink) and 925–960 MHz (downlink), adding 50 channels (channel numbers 975 to 1023 and

0) to the original GSM-900 band. Time division multiplexing is used to allow eight full-rate or sixteen half-rate speech channels per radio frequency channel. There are eight radio timeslots (giving eight burst periods) grouped into what is called a TDMA frame. Half rate channels use alternate frames in the same timeslot. The channel data rate is 270.833 kbit/s, and the frame duration is 4.615 ms.

CONCLUSION

SSD and Faster RCNN algorithms are simulated for pre labeled and self-created image dataset for weapon (gun) detection. Both the algorithms are efficient and give good results but their application in real time is based on a tradeoff between speed and accuracy. In terms of speed, SSD algorithm gives better speed with 0.736 s/frame. Whereas Faster RCNN gives speed 1.606s/frame, which is poor compared to SSD. With respect to accuracy, Faster RCNN gives better accuracy of 84.6%. Whereas SSD gives an accuracy of 73.8%, which is poor compared to faster RCNN. SSD provided real time detection due to faster speed but Faster RCNN provided superior accuracy. Further, it can be implemented for larger datasets by

training using GPUs and high-end DSP and FPGA kits.

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